

IMPACT OF LAYUP RATE ON QUALITY OF FIBER STEERING/CUT-RESTART IN AUTOMATED FIBER PLACEMENT PROCESS

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1 Introduction

Cost-effective manufacturing of high quality aerospace composite parts can be achieved through part design and integration as well as through automation of manufacturing processes. Automated composites manufacturing decrease labor intensity and make it possible to integrate composite structures by minimizing the number of parts and assembly cost; it can also increase part reproducibility and productivity. Currently, the automated fiber placement (AFP) process has drawn the attention of commercial airplane manufacturers from worldwide and has been used to manufacture large scale composite structures, such as composite fuselages. Fiber placement technology is a highly automated manufacturing process for fabrication of composite structures. During the AFP process, individual narrow prepreg tows are pulled from spools and fed through a fiber delivery system into a fiber placement head, in which these narrow tows are aligned into a wider band and laminated onto a tool surface. When fiber is placed, each tow of the wider band fibers is dispensed at its own speed, allowing each one to independently conform to the male (mandrel) or female mold surface. Because of this, the fibers are not restricted to geodesic paths and they can be steered to meet specified design goals.

Although automated fiber placement has many advantages, there are limitations: Part quality is strongly influenced by processing parameters such as torch temperature, layup speed, fiber tension, and compaction pressure, etc. Furthermore, fiber paths planning and AFP programming strategies have a

direct impact on the productivity and quality of fiber-placed parts. For example, if there is a cut-out in the part, a trade-off study should be carried out to decide whether the cut-out should be made during the AFP process or after the part is cured. Moreover, part geometry as well as tooling concept has an influence on fiber placement process. It is known that the AFP process can only handle complex geometries to a certain degree. Both quality and layup rate are severely impacted by the complexity of a part [1, 2]. For complex-shaped composite structures, in order to keep desired fiber orientation, fiber steering is unavoidable. Although most of the AFP machines have the capability to steer fibers on the tool surface along designed fiber axis [3, 4], over-steered fibers can pose problems, resulting in local wrinkles and separation of fibers from the substrate [5]. Besides, researches show that properly utilizing the fiber steering capabilities of a fiber placement machine can enlarge design flexibility and create more efficient composite structures [6, 7]. Therefore, understanding fiber steering in the AFP process is very beneficial for composite structures design and manufacturing.

In this study, both simulation and experimental study were conducted to investigate the impact of layup rate on quality of fiber steering and fiber cut/restart across cut-outs in the automated fiber placement process. Different conditions were selected to evaluate the layup quality. A series of curve fiber paths were designed for the fiber steering study. Finally, laminates were fiber placed to evaluate the quality of fiber steering and cut/restart at different layup rates.

2. Fiber Placement Simulation

2.1 Trial Description

Two fiber steering trials were conducted under different layup rates. In the first trial, the guide curves of the fiber paths consisted of three sections: two straight line sections and one arc (illustrated in Figure 1a). The radius of the arcs, R , was varied from 114mm to 785mm with a step of 28mm. In addition to the variable radius, the length of the arcs was varied, resulting in different angles ($\theta = 5, 10, 15, \text{ and } 20$ degree) between the two straight line sections. The dimension of the laminate is approximately 380mm x 635mm. In the second trial, fiber steering with sinusoidal fiber paths was tested, as shown in Figure 1b. The amplitude of the sine waves, A , was 31.5 mm, and the wavelength, λ , ranged from 700 mm to 1750 mm.

Fig.1. Fiber steering (a) trial 1; (b) trial 2

The purposes of the fiber steering trials was to explore the possibility of layup steered fibers under different layup speeds, and to compare the simulation results obtained from fiber placement software with experimental results.

Figure 2 shows the configuration of the laminates for the cut/restart trials. Six scenarios were defined to test layup accuracy of one /bi-directional layup at different layup speeds (6, 18 and 30 m/min). The blue area is the dimension of the laminates and the green lines are marked references for measurement. The influence of the cut-outs on AFP productivity is also studied.

Fig.2. Cut/restart trial

2.2 Simulation of AFP Process

2.2.1 Fiber Steering

MAG's ACES programming/simulation software is used to generate the fiber paths and to simulate the fiber steering. Figure 3 and Figure 4 show the simulation results of AFP lay-up along curved fiber paths, which clearly indicate three regions on the laminates: a processable area with quality concern (orange color), an area with quality problems (red color), and a region free of problems (other colors). It should be noted that those colored areas were generated according to MAG's predefined criteria. For a 3.2 mm wide prepreg tow, the minimum requirement for radius of curvature (ROC) is 635 mm (recommended by MAG) for laying prepreg tows onto a surface without wrinkles and buckling. Thus, if the radius of curvature of a fiber path is smaller than 635 mm, the centerline of the fiber path will be shown in red color in the simulated results, indicating that there will be unavoidable process problems in these areas; and these problems can only be resolved by either reducing material width or increasing radius of curvature in the design. Figure 3a shows that when $\theta = 5^\circ$, it is feasible to layup the laminate. In this case, it was predicted that there will be no unavoidable AFP related quality problems, even if the ROC is smaller than 635 mm. However, it should be noted that in Figure 3a, orange color is shown in the middle of the courses, which means optimized processing parameters (e.g., temperatures, pressure and speed, etc.) have to be

IMPACT OF LAYUP RATE ON QUALITY OF FIBER STEERING/CUT-RESTART IN AUTOMATED FIBER PLACEMENT PROCESS

used to ensure the quality of the laminate. Figure 3b shows that when $\theta = 10^\circ$, only the last four courses can be processed without major quality issues.

Fig. 3. Simulation results of fiber steering trial 1

Fig. 4. Simulation results of fiber steering trial 2

The red areas in Figure 3c and Figure 3d indicate that, when $\theta \geq 15^\circ$, quality problems in fiber steering are unavoidable. Figure 4 shows simulation results of fiber steering with sinusoidal fiber paths. It was predicted that the first three courses at the top will not be processable by AFP because of quality problems that will be introduced.

2.2.2 Cut/restart

In the simulation of cut/restart trials, two scenarios were studied. In scenario 1, the compaction roller of the AFP machine retracts from the surface when the head reaches the boundary of the cut-outs during the layup. In scenario 2, the compaction roller stays on surface inside the cut-outs. Simulation showed that in both cases, the Viper 4000 AFP machine can lay down the shortest courses with a length of 113 mm. Due to the distance between the cutter and the feed roller of the AFP machine, the yellow area shown in Figure 5 cannot be covered by carbon prepreg courses laid by the fiber placement machine, unless a process option is enabled to force the AFP machine to lay down material with the minimum layup length.

Fig. 5. Simulation of the cut/restart trial

3. Experiment

3.1 Materials

The prepreg slit tape used in the study is intermediate modulus (IM) carbon fiber/epoxy (3.2

mm width) from Hexcel. Eight spools of materials were used in the AFP trials.

3.2 Fiber Placement Machine

A Viper 4000 fiber placement machine from MAG Cincinnati is used in the experiment, as shown in Figure 6. The working envelope of the AFP machine is 4 meters in diameter by 10 meters long. This machine has the capability to layup up to 32 tows (total width of 101.6mm) of slit tapes with controlled individual tow cut/restart. It can lay down carbon fiber prepreg tows on both convex and concave surfaces.

Fig. 6. Viper 4000 fiber placement machine

3.3 Fiber Steering Trials

Before the AFP process, the flat tool surface was covered by breather, plastic bag and peel ply in sequence. The first layer of laminate was then laid down on the peel ply.

Case 1, $\theta = 5^\circ$: Two different layup speeds, namely, 2 m/min and 10.5 m/min., were used in the case 1 study. Figure 7 shows that the quality of the first ply is relatively good, except that there are small numbers of uncompact spots in some locations, which is thought to be caused by lack of tackiness of the peel ply or low surface temperature. A wrinkled area was noticed at the top of the laminate where the fibers are straight. This could be induced by a small leak of vacuum on the plastic bag.

To test the influence of the tackiness of the substrate, a second ply was laid down directly onto ply 1. Figure 8 shows that the quality of ply 2 was improved, and no obviously uncompact spots

were observed. However, the wrinkled areas were enlarged in the second ply because of the shift of the substrate due to the vacuum leaks or deformation of the vacuum bag.

To avoid the wrinkles caused by the small shift of the vacuum bag during the layup, a rigid plastic material was used to replace the vacuum bag. Thus, the prepreg was laid on a surface which is covered by breather, rigid plastic, and peel ply in sequence. The trial was then repeated and carried out at a speed of 10.7 m/min.

Fig.7. Fiber steering trial case 1, $\theta = 5^\circ$, ply 1, laid down at 2 m/min.

Fig.8. Fiber steering trial case 1: $\theta = 5^\circ$, ply 2, laid down at 2 m/min.

IMPACT OF LAYUP RATE ON QUALITY OF FIBER STEERING/CUT-RESTART IN AUTOMATED FIBER PLACEMENT PROCESS

It can be seen in Figure 9 that there are wrinkles spreading across the ply, even in the last few courses with large radius of curvature. There are also increased gaps in the areas close to the part edges where the courses are cut. Results in Figure 9 confirm again that the quality of fiber steering is layup speed related.

Fig.9. Fiber steering trial case 1: $\theta = 5^\circ$, ply 1, laid down at 10.7 m/min.

Case 2, $\theta = 10^\circ$: It was decided to start the case 2 trial at the speed of 10.7 m/min; if there are fiber problems in the laminate, then the layup speed will be reduced in the next trial. As shown in Figure 10, there were uncompact areas (small wrinkles) across the middle of ply 1, and again, increased gaps between tows were observed at the location close to the edge of the laminate.

Fig.10. Fiber steering trial case 2: $\theta = 10^\circ$, ply 1, laid down at 10.7 m/min.

The influence of substrate on the layup quality was tested again by laying up the second ply directly on ply 1. Comparing to ply 1, the wrinkles were not reduced in the middle area of the laminate, as shown in Figure 11.

Fig.11. Fiber steering trial case 2: $\theta = 10^\circ$, ply 2, laid down at 10.7 m/min.

To test if a debulking process could help remove the uncompact spots, the two-ply laminate was debulked under full vacuum for 15 minutes. As shown in Figure 12, the situation was improved, but there are still some places not completely compacted. It is believed that this problem could be solved by extending the debulking time or increasing debulk temperature.

Fig.12. After 15 min. debulking (case 2: $\theta = 10^\circ$, ply 2, laid down at 10.7 m/min.)

Trials were carried out again by reducing the layup speed to 2 m/min., as shown in Figure 13. It can be seen that in this case, even at a slow layup speed,

wrinkles and uncompacted spots still show up, however, it is noticed that when the radius of the curve is larger than 27.6 inches, there are almost no wrinkles showing up. It is interesting to see that the simulated results in Figure 3 agree well with the results in Figure 13. Case 3 and case 4 of the fiber steering trials were skipped, since we did not expect to see any improvement over the results obtained in fiber steering trial case 2.

Fig.13. Fiber steering trial case 2: $\theta = 10^\circ$, ply 2, laid down at 2 m/min.

In the fiber steering trial 2, sinusoidal fiber paths were laid down at alternating layup speeds of 1.5 m/min and 10.7 m/min, as shown in Figure 14. Both uncompacted tows and fiber slip were observed at the two layup speeds. The highlighted area in Figure 14 is enlarged and shown in Figure 15.

Fig.14. Fiber steering trial 2: Sinusoids fiber paths

3.4 Cut/Restart

Six laminates were made to investigate the influence of layup rate on the cut/restart quality. Two scenarios are considered in the trials: In the first scenario, the compaction roller is retracted between courses. In the second scenario, the compaction roller is kept on the surface when it runs into the cut-outs.

Fig.15. Fiber steering trial 2: Sinusoids fiber paths

It can be seen from Figure 16 and Figure 17 that the quality of the tow cut is independent of the layup speed; but the quality of the tow restart, in contrast, is layup speed related. It can be seen clearly in Figure 17 that in the bi-directional trials, zigzag patterns were created along the boundaries of the cut-outs by the AFP machine at higher layup speed. The quality of tow restart could be improved by increasing the tackiness of the substrate or tool surface temperature.

Fig.16. Cut/restart trial: 6 m/min
(a) one-directional; (b) bi-directional

Fig.17. Cut/restart trial: 30 m/min
(a) one-directional; (b) bi-directional

3.5 Productivity Analysis

3.5.1 Influence of Course Division

As mentioned in section 3.4, in scenario 1 of the cut/restart trials, the compaction roller was retracted between courses (course division function enabled), while in scenario 2, the compaction roller stays on the tool surface and runs into the cut-outs. The average fiber delivery (lb/hr) in both cases is compared in Figure 18. It can be seen that in scenario 2, at the layup speed of 6 m/min., the material yield is more than twice that obtained in scenario 1, with a higher layup speed of 10.7 m/min. To avoid confusion, material yield in this paper is normalized to fiber placement with 32 tows.

Fig.18. Influence of course division on material yield

It should be noted that in scenario 1, the material yield is also a function of the distance that the head is retracted from the surface. Therefore, appropriate retract distance should be selected in the AFP programming.

3.5.2 Influence of Part Design

It is known that part design has an impact on AFP productivity. Studies were carried out to compare the material yield, with and without cut-outs, for the laminate shown in Figure 2. Results are shown in Figure 19. Without the cut-outs, the AFP processing time will be reduced by 18%; however, 24% more materials will be needed to manufacture the laminate.

Fig.19. Influence of cut-outs on material yield at layup rate of 18 m/min.

3.5.3 Influence of One/Bi-directional Layup

The influence of one/bi-directional layup on AFP productivity is presented in Table 1. It can be seen in Table 1 that when the layup speed increased from 6 m/min to 18 m/min, the material yield increased by about 20%; however, there is no increase in material yield when the layup speed increased from 18 m/min to 30 m/min. Also, the material yield in the one-directional layup is always higher than in the bi-directional layup. These results suggest that the size of the laminate is too small to take advantage of either the high speed or the bi-directional layup. It is also noted from results in Table 1 that the material yields (lb/hr) predicted by the ACE software have the same trend, but higher than the actual amounts. The material yields is process related and cannot be accurately predicted.

Table 1 Comparison of Material Yield

Part Nr.	Description	Average Material Yield (ACES Predicted) lbs/hr	Average Material Yield (Actual) lbs/hr
1	6 m/min, one directional	8.12	6.72
2	6 m/min, bi-directional	7.92	6.28
3	18 m/min, one directional	10.52	8.0
4	18 m/min, bi-directional	10.12	7.76
5	30 m/min, one directional	10.72	7.76
6	30 m/min, bi-directional	10.24	7.52

4 Conclusions

The following conclusions can be drawn from this study:

1. The experimental results are in good agreement with the ACES software prediction for the fiber steering trials.
2. In fiber steering trial 1, in the areas with quality concern (simulation predicted), the layup speed has to be kept as low as 1.5 m/min to ensure a good part quality. It was observed that the quality of fiber steering is influenced by the tackiness of the substrate. Debulking process can reduce the number of uncompacted spots.
3. In fiber steering trial 2, tow pull up and fiber slip were observed in the area which was predicted to be problem free, even at a low layup speed. This could be attributed to the internal stress caused by fiber tension. Further studies are needed to investigate the influences of process conditions on sinusoidal fiber steering.
4. Results of cut/restart trials showed that the quality of tow cut is not affected by layup rate, however, the accuracy of tow restart depends on the layup rate. Higher layup rate has a negative impact on the accuracy of the fiber restart.
5. Course division, part design (e.g., with/without cut-outs) and layup strategies (e.g., one/bi-directional layup) have an impact on AFP productivity. A trade-off study is necessary

before full implementation of the AFP manufacturing process.

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